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2 **Not Only Priming: Soil Microbiota May Protect Tomato from Root Pathogens**

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27 **Keywords:** *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici*; arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; defence

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29 responses; lignin biosynthesis; microbiota; suppressive and conducive soils; susceptible and

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31 resistant genotypes; tomato; gene expression.

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35 Correspondence to:

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43 **Abstract**

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45 An increasing number of studies have investigated soil microbial biodiversity. However, the

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47 mechanisms regulating plant responses to soil microbiota are largely unknown. A previous work

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49 tested the hypothesis that tomato plants grown on native soils with their complex microbiotas

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24 respond differently from tomato growing in a sterile substrate. Two soils, suppressive or conducive
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225 to *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (FOL), and two genotypes susceptible and resistant to the
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526 same pathogen were considered. The work highlighted that the two tested soil microbiotas,
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727 irrespectively of their taxonomic composition, elicit the PAMP-triggered Immunity Pathway, the
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1028 first level of plant defence, as well as an increased lignin synthesis, leading to an active protection
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1229 when FOL is present in the soil. Here, we tested the expression of a panel of genes involved in
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1430 Effector-Triggered Immunity (ETI), demonstrating that soil microbiota, beside genotype, affects
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1731 plant resistance to FOL also modulating this pathway.

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21 2233 **TEXT**

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2434 Next-generation sequencing (NGS) has enabled in-depth investigations of the microbial
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2735 communities associated with animals, plants, and fungi. The awareness that multicellular
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2936 eukaryotes host thousands of microbes, many beneficial, some essential and only a few deleterious
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3237 has led to a paradigm shift in our knowledge of microbial–eukaryote interactions. NGS approaches
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3438 helped us to reply to basic questions of traditional microbiology, as: ‘Which are the microbes
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3639 thriving in that niche?’, and ‘What are they doing?’. Focusing on the plant side and starting from
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3940 the pioneering researches by Bulgarelli et al.¹ and Lundberg et al.², many other studies revealed the
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4141 extraordinary diversity of microbes present on both roots, shoots, leaves, fruits^{3,4}, and demonstrated
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4442 how different parameters affect the composition of the microbiota: plant genotype, soil features,
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4643 environmental parameters^{5,6}. Interestingly, the environment resulted to be the driving force also for
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4944 human microbiota, where it dominates over host genetics in shaping human gut microbiota⁷. The
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5145 strict relationship existing between microbiota and their eukaryotic host has also led to the
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5446 development of the *holobiont* concept^{8,9}. Host-microbial systems, being a complex assembly of
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5647 diverse organisms, constitute unique biological entities, defined as ‘meta-organisms’ or holobionts¹⁰.
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5848 However, metagenomic sequencing has only given indirect responses to the questions opened by
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49 these new scenarios: ‘How the host responds to its extended microbiota, which represents its second
1 genome?’.
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752 Chialva et al.¹¹ focused on tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*), testing the hypothesis that plants grown
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1053 on native soils display different responses to soil microbiotas. Using transcriptomics, proteomics,
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1254 and biochemistry, the study has described the responses of two tomato genotypes (susceptible or
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1455 resistant to FOL) grown on two native soils (conducive and suppressive to FOL) and an artificial
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1756 substrate. Results showed that native soils, particularly the suppressive one, affect tomato responses
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1957 by modulating pathways involved in responses to oxidative stress, phenol biosynthesis, lignin
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2258 deposition, and PAMP-triggered Immunity (PTI). By contrast, in tomato plants grown on steam-
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2459 disinfected soils, total phenols and PTI responses significantly decreased, suggesting a crucial role
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2760 of soil microbiota in eliciting a priming effect. To validate those observations, the mycorrhizal
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2961 fungus *Funnelliformis mosseae*, was selected as one of the most abundant AM fungi in both soils,
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3262 and inoculated in tomato growing on steam-disinfected soils: the fungal inoculation partly rescued
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3463 some of the local and systemic responses, which were identified as a part of the priming response.
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3664 Martinez-Medina et al.¹² have neatly identified different conditions where plant defence priming
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3965 takes place and have acknowledged many beneficial microbes as a source for priming stimuli.
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4166 Indeed, under the tested experimental conditions (native soils vs sterile substrate), tomato activates
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4467 several genes involved in PTI, such as those encoding for PR proteins, WRKY transcription factors,
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4668 ROS burst signalling and calcium signalling, which are involved in immune response¹³. To
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4969 understand whether such an adaptive measure leads the plant to an enhanced defence readiness¹¹
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5170 tomato plants were inoculated with FOL. As expected, reduced disease symptoms were detected in
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5371 the resistant genotype ('Battito') in both soils; but surprisingly the susceptible genotype 'Cuore di
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5672 Bue' was partially protected from FOL on the suppressive soil. However, it is still unknown whether

73 the Effector-Triggered Immunity (ETI), *i.e.* the second barrier against pathogens, responds to soil
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274 microbiota.
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776 Here, we hypothesized that the priming status raised in tomato by soil microbiota could elicit the
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1077 expression of genes directly involved in ETI in the presence of FOL. With this aim, we selected a
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1278 panel of genes involved in the ETI pathway (Table 1) and tested their expression by using RT-
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1479 qPCR in FOL-inoculated plant roots according to the set-up and methods described in Chialva et
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1780 al.¹¹.
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2282 Results indicate that soil microbiota promoted the ETI response of plants after FOL infection (Fig.
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2483 1): while in RNA-seq experiment, where FOL was not present, ETI genes were not differentially
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2784 expressed, in FOL-inoculated plants RT-qPCR experiment detected gene modulation¹¹. Both
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2985 genotypes significantly upregulated the expression of *RIN4* ($p < 0.05$) in both native soils compared
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3286 to the control substrate. This protein is a target of type III pili effector proteins (virulence factors)
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3487 from bacterial pathogens and interacts with RPS2 and RPM1 R protein leading to hypersensitive
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3688 response^{14,15}. Moreover, we tested the expression of two previously described ETI-marker genes¹⁶
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3989 and found that one of them coding for a UDP-glucosyltransferase family 1 protein (UDP) is
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4190 upregulated in both soils ($p < 0.05$) with the exception of the susceptible cultivar in the conducive
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4491 soil. However, the other marker gene tested (UDP1) did not show differential expression across
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4692 conditions. By contrast, the expression of the *I-2* R gene, directly involved in FOL race 2¹⁷, was
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4993 upregulated only in the resistant genotype grown in the suppressive soil, while it remained
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5194 consistent for the susceptible genotype in all the substrates. These results suggest a synergy between
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5395 the genotype (presence of Resistance genes), the soil biological features, and – mechanistically –
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5696 the ETI response. The 'Cuore di Bue' susceptible genotype has a more modulated response: FOL-
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5897 suppressive soil with its microbiota activates the ETI response, while this action is not elicited in
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98 the conducive soil. This well explains the modulation of *I-2 R* gene: to be activated, plant defences
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299 require the suppressive soil microbiota acting on the resistant genotype, while the synergy between
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4100 these two conditions is not satisfied in the susceptible genotype. The hypothesis may have an
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7101 experimental validation by the presence of many bio-control *Fusaria* strains isolated in the
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9102 Albenga soil¹⁸.

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14104 Our previous experiments demonstrated that soil microbiota leads to a priming ('state of alert') in
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17105 tomato eliciting the PTI, which represents the first level of plant defence. When challenged by a
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19106 pathogen, the alerted plant activates a new set of more specific genes related to the ETI, which is
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22107 the second specific defence level (Fig. 2). This mechanism leads to a partial protection from the
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24108 pathogen attack, even in the absence of specific resistance genes (as for the cultivar 'Cuore di Bue').

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26109 The modulation of the ETI-related genes indicates that native soil microbiota also affects plant
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29110 response to FOL via ETI, in addition to the crucial role played by the genotype.

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31111 In conclusion, the investigation of the mechanisms operating in plants in native soils and in the
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34112 presence of complex soil microbiota has revealed new unexpected responses. It seems that - just
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36113 like humans - the tomato plant living in non-sterile conditions can better activate its immunity
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39114 defence via the interaction with its microbiota.

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42 43 44116 **Disclosure of potential conflicts of interest**

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46117 No potential conflicts of interest were disclosed.

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50 51119 **Acknowledgments**

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56121 experiments.

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Figure Legends

Figure 1.

RT-qPCR relative expression levels of gene involved in ETI in tomato plants (*Solanum lycopersicum*) infected with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (FOL).

Ubiquitin gene was used as reference for RT-qPCR. Letters indicate statistically supported differences (Kruskal–Wallis test at $P < 0.05$). Data are means \pm SE (n = 3). AL, ‘Albenga’ suppressive soil; RO, ‘Rosta’ conducive soil; CONT, Control 'Neutral' soil. B, 'Battito' FOL-resistant genotype; C, 'Cuore di Bue' FOL-susceptible genotype. (A) *RIN4*, RPM1 interacting protein 4; (B) *I-2*, CC-NBS-LRR, resistance protein 1; (B,C) *UDP*, *UDP1*, UDP-glucosyltransferase family 1 proteins.

Figure 2

Scheme of defence responses activated by tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) in the presence of a complex native soil microbiota.

(1) According to the models proposed by Chialva et al.,¹¹ in native soils microbial-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs) such as flagellin (flg22) and chitin are perceived by tomato plant. Those events elicit the PTI pathway (Plant-triggered Immunity) as a first defence level with the activation of calcium signalling (CNGCs, cyclic nucleotide-gated channels; CaM/CaM-like (CML), calmodulin-like proteins; CDPKs, calcium-dependent protein kinases) and WRKY transcription factors. This brings to the downstream activation of pathogenesis-related proteins genes (PR), such

166 as PR1, and to cell-wall fortification and lignin synthesis. (2) Since PTI-related defence is elicited, a
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267 “continuative priming” by soil microbiota components occurs, maintaining plant defence active. (3)
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568 When plant is attacked by *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp *lycopersici* (FOL) the plant is already primed
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769 and activates stronger ETI (Effector-triggered Immunity) defence. In both genotypes, effectors are
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1070 strongly perceived (e.g. by *RIN4*): only in the FOL-resistant one a specific resistance mediated by *I*-
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1271 2 is activated leading to the activation of the downstream ETI responses (such as UDP
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1572 upregulation). However, in the susceptible genotype even if *I*-2 upregulation was not observed,
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1773 FOL-suppressive soil induced the activation of downstream ETI pathway with the upregulation of a
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1974 marker UDP gene.

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Table 1. Table of primers used in RT-qPCR experiment.

Gene	Transcript ID	Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (5'-3')	Reference
RPM1	Solyc11g0120	TCCTTCTGTAGAGTCGG	TCTTCTTCGTCGTGTTG	¹¹
interacting protein 4 (<i>RIN4</i>)	10.1	GCCA	GTTGGT	
CC-NBS-LRR, resistance protein 1 (<i>I-2</i>)	Solyc11g0714	TTTGAAAGGGTCCCAA	TGCAGAGGGGTGTCAA	This study
UDP-glucosyltransferase family 1 protein (UDP)	Solyc10g0858	CAAAGCTGAAAGAGGG	TAACCCAAGCCCTAGCT	This study
UDP-	Solyc09g0925	GGTGCAACCCCATGTC	ATCAGAGAATGCCGCC	This

1	glucosyltransf	00.1	CTATTG	AAGT	study
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4	protein				
5	(UDP1)				
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Figure

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